

Reductive cyclodimerization of arylmethylidenemalononitriles promoted by AlCl_3/Sm system : a facile synthesis of cyclopentamine derivatives

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Promoted by AlCl_3/Sm bimetallic system, α,β -unsaturated nitriles undergo reductive cyclodimerization to afford cyclopentamine derivatives under mild conditions.

Carbon-carbon bond formation is the essence of organic synthesis and the reductive dimerization of carbonyl derivatives by means of active metals is one of the most valuable methods for establishing carbon-carbon bonds. Recently, some reports on the reductive cyclodimerization of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl derivatives or α,β -unsaturated nitriles have been reported, providing a novel access to functionalized five-membered ring products¹.

The chemistry of aluminum has acquired renewed interest² and in recent years the versatility of aluminum chloride has been in rapid evolution. For example, Dutta and Konwar³ reported an efficient deoxygenation reaction of nitrones and heteroarenes *N*-oxides induced by $\text{Zn-AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ bimetallic system. Similarly, this system has been used in the reductive cleavage of 2,1-benzisoxazole to give *ortho*-amino- and *N*-alkylaminobenzophenones⁴. Most recently, a novel method for the reductive coupling of carbonyl compounds to olefins promoted by $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-Zn-CH}_3\text{CN}$ system has also been reported⁵. However, to the best of our knowledge, no example for the reductive cyclodimerization of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl derivatives or α,β -unsaturated nitriles has been reported with this reagent. Herein we describe our preliminary results on a novel utility of AlCl_3 and metal samarium as an efficient reagent for the intermolecular reductive cyclodimerization of arylmethylidenemalononitriles to give cyclopentamine derivatives (Scheme 1). The results are shown in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

When α,β -unsaturated nitriles (1) were treated with AlCl_3/Sm bimetallic system in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran,

Scheme 1

the intermolecular reductive cyclodimerization products 2-amino-1,3,3-tricyano-4,5-diarylcyclopentenes (2) were obtained in moderate to good yields. Through careful separation of the reaction mixture, only one isomer, the 4,5-*trans*-isomer was obtained, indicating that this cyclodimerization process is highly stereoselective. The assignments of the structure of 2 are based on their physical data and spectral characteristics, which are all in agreement with the literature data^{1c}.

Table 1. Preparation of cyclopentamines promoted by Sm/AlCl_3

Compd. no.	Ar	Time h	Yield ^a %	M.p. ^c °C
2a	C_6H_5	3	71, 0 ^b	127–128 (128–130)
2b	3- BrC_6H_4	3	82	115–117 (116–118)
2c	4- ClC_6H_4	3	78	158–160 (158–160)
2d	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	3	79	188–189 (190–192)
2e	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4$	3	85	94–96 (95–97)
2f	3,4- $\text{OCH}_2\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3$	3	67	165–167 (166–168)
2g	2-furyl	5	70	123–125 (125–127)

^aIsolated yield of cyclopentamine derivatives. ^bIn the presence of Sm powder or AlCl_3 alone. ^cLit. m.p. in parenthesis (Ref. 1c).

Table 1 summarize the results on the reaction of a number of substrates. The chloro, bromo and alkoxy groups of

the substrates were tolerated under the reaction conditions. In addition, it should be noted that no reaction took place with either metal samarium or aluminum trichloride alone (Table 1, Entry 2a).

Although the detailed mechanism of the above reaction has not been clarified yet, according to the previous work of our group⁵, it is proposed that the reaction may proceed via a single-electron transfer (SET) process (Scheme 2), with Al^{0,6}, which is generated *in situ* from the reaction of metal samarium with aluminum chloride, supplying electrons to substrate **1** to generate radical anion **A**. Radical anion **A** then abstracts a proton from solvent (THF) to form radical **B**. Promoted by Al⁰, radical **B** dimerizes with substrate **1** to give anion **C**, which undergoes ring closure reaction to yield aminocyclopentene derivatives (**2**).

Based on the mechanism depicted in Scheme 2, the observed stereoselectivity of the reaction can be explained by the existence of two different conformations for the anionic intermediate (**C**). Conformation **I**, being non-eclipsed, may be favored since two aryl groups are in *anti*-positions and the steric interactions are minimized. Thus, when the five-membered ring is formed, the *trans*-conformation product should be obtained. On the other hand, the eclipsed conformation (**II**), from which the *cis*-product would be obtained, is much less favored since the steric interactions are maximized (the two aryl groups being in *syn*-positions). In fact, no *cis*-product has been obtained in our experiments.

In conclusion, we have provided a new route to cyclopentamine derivatives, the advantages of which include high yields, simple and mild reaction conditions, and high chemo- and stereoselectivity. Further studies to develop other new uses of AlCl₃ and Sm bimetallic system are now in progress in our laboratory.

Scheme 2

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran was distilled from sodium-benzophenone prior to use. All reactions were conducted under a nitrogen atmosphere. M.ps. were obtained on an electrothermal apparatus and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-408 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AC-400 (400 MHz) spectrometer, chemical shifts being expressed in ppm downfield from internal tetramethylsilane.

Cyclopentamine derivatives General procedure : A mixture of powdered Sm (0.3 g, 2 mmol), AlCl₃ (0.2 g, 1.5 mmol) and THF (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h under nitrogen atmosphere, then cooled to room temperature, when a black slurry was formed. Then a solution of α,β -unsaturated nitrile (1 mmol) in THF was added dropwise to it in 5 min. After stirring for 3 h, the mixture was quenched with dil. HCl (0.1 mol dm⁻³; 5 ml) and extracted with ether (3 × 20 ml). The combined extract was washed with saturated brine (15ml) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After evaporating the solvent under reduced pressure, the resulting crude product was purified by preparative TLC on silica gel using ethyl acetate-cyclohexane (1 : 4) as eluent. All the products were identified : **2a**^{1c}, ν_{\max} 3385, 3230 (NH₂), 2212 (CN), 1668 cm⁻¹ (C=C-NH₂), δ 3.78 (1H, d, *J* 9.4 Hz, ArCH), 4.48 (1H, d, *J* 9.4 Hz, ArCH), 5.31 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.12–7.68 (10H, m, ArH); **2b**^{1c}, ν_{\max} 3378, 3220 (NH₂), 2210 (CN), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=C-NH₂), δ 3.65 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, ArCH), 4.50 (1H, d, *J* 9.4 Hz, ArCH), 5.45 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.10–7.68 (8H, m, ArH); **2c**^{1c}, ν_{\max} 3380, 3270 (NH₂), 2215 (CN), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=C-NH₂), δ 3.75 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, ArCH), 4.51 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, ArCH), 5.49 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.01–7.60 (8H, m, ArH); **2d**^{1c}, ν_{\max} 3375, 3260 (NH₂), 2220 (CN), 1665 cm⁻¹ (C=C-NH₂), δ 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.32 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.78 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, ArCH), 4.53 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, ArCH), 5.42 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.02–7.45 (8H, m, ArH); **2e**^{1c}, ν_{\max} 3385, 3290 (NH₂), 2215 (CN), 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=C-NH₂), δ 3.73 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.17 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, ArCH), 4.49 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, ArCH), 5.33 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.79–7.41 (8H, m, ArH); **2f**^{1c}, ν_{\max} 3385, 3280 (NH₂), 2210 (CN), 1678 cm⁻¹ (C=C-NH₂), δ 4.16 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, ArCH), 4.43 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, ArCH), 5.45 (2H, br s, NH₂), 5.92 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 5.97 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.26–6.82 (6H, m, ArH); **2g**^{1c}, ν_{\max} 3390, 3285 (NH₂), 2218 (CN), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=C-NH₂), δ 4.20 (1H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz, ArCH), 4.63 (1H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz, ArCH), 5.64 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.34–7.58 (6H, m, ArH).

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